

A Clinical Study of Acute Appendicitis for Early Diagnosis and Management

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Abstract:

Background: Acute appendicitis remains one of the most common surgical diseases faced by the surgeons in practice. It is most common surgical emergency that performed. The diagnosis of acute appendicitis is however challenging, it remained essentially clinical knowledge, a mixture of observation, radiological imaging and reminder of art surgical diagnosis. The main aim to conduct this prospective observational study of acute appendicitis is for early diagnosis and intervention to avoid complications. This studies aim is to early diagnosis and management of acute appendicitis patients admit under General Surgery Dept. Gauhati Medical College & Hospital, Guwahati, Assam.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in the Department of Surgery; Gauhati Medical College during the period 1st may 2021 to 30th April, 2022. It was a prospective observational study. Total 50 patients admitted with clinical and radiological diagnosis of acute appendicitis, under the Department of Surgery were included in the study.

Results: Acute appendicitis is more common in males than females and the highest incidence is in 2nd and 3rd decade of life. 26 Male and 24 Female patients having a ratio of 1.08:1. The patients presented with symptoms of pain in RIF (98%) of patients followed by anorexia (54%), nausea and vomiting (66%). RIF tenderness present in 100% of patients. The patients were examined clinically thoroughly by using modified Alvarado Scoring system, 48% of the patients shown modified Alvarado score >7 and among 71.4% in male and 70% were female patients. The patients were subjected to investigation like routine blood examination, total count >10000 in 56% of patients. Ultrasonography has diagnosed 58% of cases as acute appendicitis 19 of the total cases which had Alvarado score of >7 was managed surgically and the remaining all patients with score of <7 also operated because of clinical symptoms and signs. C T scan was advised for selected patients only. All the cases were confirmed for diagnosis of acute appendicitis based on intraoperative and histopathological findings. Out of 50 patients 45 patients did not have any complication, 3 patients were having gangrenous appendix and 2 patients were having perforated appendix intraoperatively. Histopathologically confirmed cases were 70.8% and overall negative appendicectomy rate in 6% in females and 4% in male

Conclusion: Ultrasonography increases the diagnostic accuracy in the patients with suspected acute appendicitis. The modified Alvarado scoring system combined with ultrasonography can therefore be used as an inexpensive way of confirming acute appendicitis reducing negative appendicectomy rate. Currently, CT and graded compression colour Doppler ultrasonography are generally employed to aid in the diagnosis.

Keywords: Acute appendicitis, Appendicectomy, Ultrasonography, Alvarado Scoring.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis remains one of the most common surgical diseases faced by the surgeons in practice. It is most common surgical emergency that performed. It is responsible for approx 300,000 hospitalisation annually [1]. It is estimated that as much as 6% to 7% of the general population will

develop appendicitis during their life time. [2]. the diagnosis of acute appendicitis is however challenging, its remained essentially clinical knowledge, a mixture of observation, radiological imaging and reminder of art surgical diagnosis. The ratio of 1.4: 1, (male -8.6% and female -6.7%) has

developed acute appendicitis [3]. As the diagnosis error is common, the negative rate of appendectomy of 20% was accepted to avoid complication of acute appendicitis. The investigation like ultrasonography, CT scan has reduced the negative appendectomy rate from 7% to 1.7%. There have been several clinical and laboratories base scoring system for to early diagnosis and intervention of acute appendicitis.

The most widely accepted scoring system are

a) Modified Alvarado Score (1987), total score of 10, a score 7 or 8 out of 10 indicate acute appendicitis and required early intervention [4].

b) TNANAKIS (2005) scoring system with four variables and a total score of 15 points. It is a combination of clinical features, laboratory markers and ultrasonography finding. If the score is > 8, diagnosis to be appendicitis.[5]

c) RIPASA scoring system (Raja Isteri Pengiran Anak Saleha Appendicitis score): It was introduced in 2010 especially for Asian population, with 14 parameters. An additional parameter of “foreign residents” can be included to the score in countries where there is a large foreign work force who have to pay for any health care treatment. The total score is 16.5 and the optimal cut off score is 8.5[6].

The diagnosis of any form of appendicular pathology is primarily clinical. The radiological and blood investigation has improved the rate of misdiagnosis.

Sequelae of acute appendicitis: resorption; relapse and recurrent appendicitis appendicular mass; appendicular abscess, perforation – has got 20% mortality peritonitis; septicaemia, portal pyaemia, intestinal obstruction due to obstructive ileus, inflammatory adhesion, formation of band between appendix and omentum or between appendix and small bowel.

The main aim to conduct this prospective observational study of acute appendicitis is for early diagnosis and intervention to avoid complications. This study aims to early diagnosis and management

of acute appendicitis patients admit under General Surgery Dept, Guahati Medical College & Hospital, Guwahati, Assam.

Aims and Objectives:

1. To assess the symptoms and signs of acute appendicitis.
2. Early diagnosis and management of acute appendicitis.
3. To evaluate complications of acute appendicitis.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Surgery, Gauhati Medical College during the period 1st may 2021 to 30th April, 2022. it was a prospective observational study. Total 50 patients admitted with clinical and radiological diagnosis of acute appendicitis, under the Department of Surgery were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients admitted with the clinical symptoms and signs of acute appendicitis within 24-48 hours.
2. Age more than 12 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. All patients other than acute appendicitis are excluded.
2. Pain abdomen more than 48 hours.
3. Prediagnosed Appendicular Mass
4. Age below 12 years

Ethical clearance was obtained from “Ethical Clearance Committee” of the institution for the study. Based on the selection criteria and exclusion criteria the patients admitted with clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis and study was conducted

Results and Observation:

In this series of 50 cases, all the patients who presented with acute symptoms and signs diagnosis to have acute appendicitis were included in the study.

Table 1: Distribution of Age and Sex in Modified Alvarado scoring

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
12 – 20	4 (36.4%)	7 (63.6%)	11 (22%)
21 – 30	20 (64.5%)	11 (35.4%)	31 (62%)
31 – 40	2 (40%)	3 (60%)	5 (10%)
41 – 50	0	2 (100%)	2 (4%)
51 - 60	0	1 (100%)	1 (2%)
Total	26	24	50 (100%)

Table 2: Distribution of patients as per modified Alvarado scoring male and female ratio

Sex	No of patients	Percentage	M:F Ratio
Male	26	52%	1.08:1
Female	24	48%	
Total	50	100%	

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to modified Alvarado scoring

Table 3:

Sex	No of cases with score (1-4)	No of cases with score (5-6)	No of cases With score (7-9)	Total	Percentage
Male	7	5	14	26	52%
Female	6	8	10	24	48%
Total	13	13	24	50	100%

In this series of 50 cases, 14(53%) patients were modified ALVARDO score >7 out of 26(male) and 10 (41.6%) patients were modified ALVARDO score >7 out of 24(females) patients. Graph showing Sex Distribution with Modified Alvarado Scoring

Figure 2: Sex Distribution with Modified Alvarado Scoring

In our study the distribution of the patients according to Modified Alvarado Score in >7 range is 24.

Table 4:

Score	No of patients	Percentage
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	5	10%
4	8	16%
5	5	10%
6	8	16%
7	12	24%
8	7	14%
9	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Table 5: Symptoms Distribution with Modified Alvarado Scoring

Symptoms	No of cases with Score (1-4)	No of cases with score (5-6)	No of cases with score (7-9)	Total	Percentage
Migration of pain to right iliac fossa	12	13	24	49	100%
Anorexia	0	6	21	27	54%
Nausea and vomiting	7	9	17	33	66%

Table 6: Distribution of signs

Signs	No of cases with score (1-4)	No of cases with score (5-6)	No of cases with score (7-9)	Total	Percentage
Tenderness right Iliac fossa	13	13	24	50	100%
Rebound tenderness	1	5	13	19	38%
Elevated temperature >37deg C	1	6	14	21	42%

Right Iliac Fossa Tenderness: On clinical examination of the patients, tenderness present in RIF with 100% was most consistent feature followed by elevated temperature 42% and rebound tenderness 38%.

Table 7: White blood cell count and cases of leucocytosis

Lab diagnosis	No of cases with score (1-4)	No of cases with score (5-6)	No of cases with score (7-9)	Total	Percentage
Leukocytosis	0	4	24	28	56%

Table 8: Laboratory Diagnosis Distribution with Modified Alvarado Scoring Distribution of Clinical Features and Lab Parameters with Sensitivity and Specificity Of Modified Alvarado Score

Features	Total Number Of Patients	Percentage	Sensitivity	Specificity
Migrating pain to RIF	49	98%	96.88%	0.00%
Nausea and Vomiting	33	66%	62.50%	27.78%
Anorexia	27	54%	62.50%	61.11%
Right iliac fossa tenderness	50	100%	100%	0.00%
Elevated temperature	21	42%	46.88%	66.67%
Rebound tenderness	19	38%	46.88%	77.78%
Leucocytosis	28	56%	56.25%	44.44%

Most consistent parameter of Alvarado scoring in the study being tenderness in the right iliac fossa (100%) followed by migratory pain (96%). Graph showing Distribution of Clinical Features and Lab Parameters with Sensitivity and Specificity of Modified Alvarado Score

Figure 3:

Table 9: Histopathology Diagnosis Distribution with modified Alvarado scoring

Modified Alvarado Score	HPR Positive	HPR Negative	Total Negative Appendicectomy Rate
>7 (24)	17 (70.83%)	7 (29.16%)	29.16%
< 7 (26)	15 (57.69%)	11 (42.30%)	42.30%
	32	18	71.46%

In our study the modified Alvarado score >7 ; 24 patients in which 17 (70.83%) were histological proved acute appendicitis and 7 (29.16%) patients were histopathologically negative. In our study the modified Alvarado score <7 is 26 patients in which 15 (57.69%) are histological proved acute appendicitis and 11 (42.30%) patients were histopathologically negative.

Table 10: Gender Distribution of results of Histopathology for patients with Modified Alvarado score ≥ 7

Gender	Positive HPR	Percentage	Negative HPR	Percentage
Female N = 10	7	41.2%	3	42.8%
Male N = 14	10	58.2%	4	57.2%
Total N = 24	17	100%	7	100%

A total of 50 patients who underwent appendicectomy, 24 patients of alvarado score >7 , 41.2%female patients and 58.2% male patients are having acute appendicitis histologically and remaining are normal appendix .

Table 11: Gender distribution of results of histopathology for all patients

Gender	Positive HPR	Percentage	Negative HPR	Percentage
Female N = 24	18	56.25%	6	33.33%
Male N = 26	14	43.75%	12	66.67%
Total N = 50	32	100%	18	100%

A total of 50 patients who underwent appendicectomy, (a) 18 (56.25%) female patients were histologically acute appendicitis and 6 (33.33%) patients are normal appendix. (b) 14 (43.75%) male patients were histologically acute appendicitis and 12 (66.67%) patients were normal appendix.

Table 12: Result of Our Treatment Plan (≥ 7)

Sex	MAS >7	USG +ve	Confirmed appendicitis
Male	14	9 (64.28%)	7 (50%)
Female	10	10 (100%)	7 (70%)
	24	19	14

A series of 50 cases: 14 male patients were MAS >7 , 64.28% ultrasonologically acute appendicitis and 50% were post operatively confirmed. 10 female patients were MAS >7 , 100% ultrasonologically acute appendicitis and 70% were post operatively confirmed.

Table 13: Results of Our Treatment Plan (<7)

Sex	MAS <7	USG +ve	Confirmed appendicitis
Male	12	5 (41.6%)	1 (8.3%)
Female	14	5 (35.7%)	4 (28.5%)
	26	10	2

A series of 50 cases; 12 male patients MAS <7 , 41.6% Ultrasonologically acute appendicitis and 8.3% were confirmed post operatively. 14 female patients MAS <7 , 35.7% Ultrasonologically acute appendicitis and 28.5% were confirmed post operatively.

Table 14: Sensitivity and specificity of our diagnostic approach in men

Diagnostic Approach result	Diagnosis		Total
	Appendicitis	Non-appendicitis	
Positive	True +ve (8)	False +ve (6)	14
Negative	False -ve (6)	True -ve (6)	12
Total	14	12	26

Table 15:

Parameter	Value	CI
Sensitivity	57.14%	28.86% to 82.34%
specificity	50.00%	21.09% to 78.91%
Positive predictive value	57.14%	39.23% to 73.36%
Negative predictive value	50.00%	30.40% to 69.60%
Accuracy	53.85%	33.37% to 73.41%

In our 50 cases series, the diagnosis approached to suspected case of appendicitis in male patients were shows 57.14% sensitivity followed by 50.00% specificity and 53.85 % accuracy in diagnosis.

Table 16: Sensitivity and specificity of our diagnostic approach in women

Diagnostic approach result	Diagnosis		Total
	Appendicitis	Non-appendicitis	
Positive	True +ve (11)	False +ve (4)	15
Negative	False -ve (7)	True -ve (2)	9
Total	18	6	24

Table 17:

Parameters	Value	CI
sensitivity	61.11%	35.75% to 82.70%
specificity	33.33%	4.33% to 77.72%
Positive predictive value	73.33%	58.33% to 84.38%
Negative predictive value	22.22%	7.42% to 50.46%
accuracy	54.17%	32.82% to 74.45%

In our 50 case series, the diagnosis approached to suspect case of acute appendicitis in female patients shows, 61.11% sensitivity followed by 33.33% specificity and diagnosis accuracy of 54.17%.

Table 18: Sensitivity and specificity of ultrasonography

Diagnostic approach result	Diagnosis		Total
	Appendicitis	Non-appendicitis	
Positive	True +ve (19)	False +ve (10)	29
Negative	False -ve (13)	True -ve (8)	21
Total	32	18	50

Table 19:

Parameters	Value	CI
sensitivity	59.38%	40.64% to 76.30%
specificity	44.44%	21.53% to 69.24%
Positive predictive value	65.52%	53.47% to 75.85%
Negative predictive value	38.10%	24.04% to 54.48%
accuracy	54.00%	39.32% to 68.19%

Our study series show 59.38% sensitivity followed by 44.44% specificity and diagnosis accuracy of 54% in suspected case of acute appendicitis of 50 samples size.

Table 20: Results of Modified Alvarado Score >7

	M A S >7	Confirmed appendicitis
Male	14	10 (71.4%)
Female	10	7 (70%)
Total	24	17

A series of 50 cases, the modified Alvarado score >7, 71.4% male patients and 70% female patients were confirmed acute appendicitis in our study.

Table 21: Results of Modified Alvarado Score <7

	M A S <7	Confirmed appendicitis
Male	12	4 (33.33%)
Female	14	11 (78.57%)
Total	26	15

A series of 50 cases, the modified Alvarado score <7, 33.33% male patients and 78.57% female patients were confirmed acute appendicitis in our study.

Table 22: Sensitivity and specificity of modified Alvarado score

Diagnostic approach result	Diagnosis		Total
	Appendicitis	Non-appendicitis	
Score ≥ 7	17	7	24
Score < 7	15	11	26
Total	32	18	50

Table 23:

Parameters	Value	CI
sensitivity	53.12%	34.74% to 70.91%
specificity	61.11%	35.75% to 82.70%
Positive predictive value	70.83%	55.55% to 82.51%
Negative predictive value	42.31%	30.33% to 55.26%
accuracy	56.00%	41.25% to 70.01%

A total of 50 series ; by using modified Alvarado scoring system for diagnosis of suspected acute appendicitis shows of 53.12% sensitivity followed by 61.11% specificity and diagnosis accuracy of 56.00% .

Table 24: Complications encountered intraoperatively

Position of Appendix	Number of patients N = 50	Percentage
Paracecal	3	6%
Retrocecal	34	68%
Pelvic	13	26%

A total of 50 cases series, the most common intraoperative appendix position is retrocecal (68%) followed by pelvic (26%) and paracecal (6%). A total of 50 cases series, the most common intraoperative appendix position is retrocecal (68%) followed by pelvic (26%) and paracecal (6%).

Figure 4: Distribution of position of appendix intraoperatively

Complications: A total of 50 cases series who underwent appendicectomy, 45(90%) patients were not encounter with any complication and 3(6%) patients including both male and female were having gangrenous appendix and 2(4%) patients were having perforated appendix intraoperatively.

Figure 5:

Discussion: A Study of 50 cases who presented with pain in right iliac fossa was conducted at Gauhati medical college and hospital, Guwahati during the study period of May 2021 to April 2022.

- Acute appendicitis is more common in males than females and the highest incidence is in 2nd and 3rd decade of life.
- 26 Male and 24 Female patients having a ratio of 1.08:1.
- The patients presented with symptoms of pain in RIF(98%) of patients followed by anorexia(54%), nausea and vomiting(66%).
- RIF tenderness present in 100% of patients.
- The patients were examined clinically thoroughly by using modified Alvarado Scoring system, 48% of the patients shown modified Alvarado score >7and among 71.4% in male and 70% were female patients.
- The patients were subjected to investigation like routine blood examination, total count >10000 in 56% of patients.
- Ultrasonography has diagnosed 58% of cases as acute appendicitis 19 of the total cases which had Alvarado score of >7 were managed surgically and the remaining all patients with score of <7 also operated because of clinical symptoms and signs.
- C T scan was advised for selected patients only.
- All the cases were confirmed for diagnosis of acute appendicitis based on intraoperative and histopathological findings. Out of 50 patients 45 patients did not have any complication, 3 patients were having gangrenous appendix and 2 patients were having perforated appendix intraoperatively.

- Histopathologically confirmed cases were 70.8% and overall negative appendectomy rate in 6% in females and 4% in male.

Conclusion: From the prospective observational study on 50 patients of acute appendicitis carried out over a period of 1 year, the following conclusion can be drawn.

- Ultrasonography increases the diagnostic accuracy in the patients with suspected acute appendicitis.
- The modified Alvarado scoring system combined with ultrasonography can therefore be used as an inexpensive way of confirming acute appendicitis reducing negative appendectomy rate.
- Currently, CT and graded compression color Doppler ultrasonography are generally employed to aid in the diagnosis.

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